

Magnetic and Optical properties of mixed oxide $(\text{KNbO}_3)_{1-x}+(\text{La}_2\text{NiMnO}_6)_x$ for photovoltaic application

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Abstract

Multiferroic perovskite oxides $(\text{KNbO}_3)_{1-x}+(\text{La}_2\text{NiMnO}_6)_x$ ($x = 0.1, 0.2$ and 0.3) with a variation of band gap have been synthesized using the solid-state reaction technique. The structural characterisation of the samples has been carried out by X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique. With the increase of $\text{La}_2\text{NiMnO}_6$ (LNMO) percentage in the solid solution, the crystal structure of KNbO_3 (KNO) becomes more symmetric from orthorhombic to cubic. Both the XRD and Raman experiment suggest the LNMO concentration dependent phase change in the KNO. The magnetic measurement (Figure) shows the ferromagnetic behaviour of the solid-solution with high Curie temperature (~ 250 K). Curie temperature, Magnetic moment and saturation magnetisation (at 80 K) increases as the percentage of LMNO in the solid-solution increases. A large reduction in the value of the band gap has been observed in the solid-solution in comparison to the band gap of KNbO_3 (~ 3.6 eV). Photoluminescence (PL) spectra reveals a strong PL quenching in the solid-solutions in comparison to the KNbO_3 . In respect of the band gap and carrier recombination rate, the solid-solutions show better photovoltaic possibility over KNbO_3 .

Fig : M-H loop at 80 K of the samples.